

ISic4355

I.Sicily inscription 4355

Language

Latin

Type

(?)

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 245

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Henzen, W., Zangemeister, K. F. W. 1872-1913. *Ephemeris epigraphica. Corporis inscriptionum Latinarum supplementum*, edita iussu Instituti archaeologici Romani. Berlin. At VIII 689
undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. Notizie degli scavi di antichità. At 386

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